

ISSN NO-2231-4687

International Journal of Management and Economics

Special Issue on Entrepreneurship

Vol. 1

No. 9

August

2013

CHETAN PUBLICATIONS AURANGABAD

50)	Social Entrepreneurship To Sustainable Development - Dr.D.B.Borade & P.N. Aute	258
51)	Problems for rural women's entrepreneurship development" - Dr Sudhir Mane	261
52)	Entrepreneurship through Self Help Groups - Dr S O Dargad & Manju Rameshchand Mutha	266
53)	Problems and prospects of women entrepreneurs in jalna city - Jitendra Marotrao Bhalerao & Chaitali Gajanan Gavali	270
54)	A study of Employee Turnover & its effect on Entrepreneurship with special reference to sewing machines Business in Aurangabad Region - Sonali Ramesh Kshirsagar	275
55)	Changing Trends in Entrepreneurship in the New Millennium - Case study of Ra.One - Amol Murgai	282
✓ 56)	Women Entrepreneurship in India-Problems and Prospects - Aruna Gangaram Pote	289
57)	Entrepreneurship in New Economic Millennium: Indian Perspective - Satish Manikrao Dhoke & Somani Pravin	295
58)	An Analytical Study of Problems & Remedies for the Development of Rural Entrepreneurship in India - Dr. M. R. Ingle & Dr. Dongardive S.V	301
59)	Women Enterpreneurship Development in India - Anand S. Bagade	306
60)	Entrepreneurship and Rural Development - Dr. B.D.Kompalwar	314
61)	Rural Entrepreneurship: A Milestone for India's Development - Dr. Shweta Patil Rajale & Dr. Amit Rajale	316

Entrepreneurship in New Economic Millennium: Indian Perspective

Satish Manikrao Dhoke

Assistant Professor

Department of Commerce,
Moreshwar Arts, Science & Commerce College,
Bhokardan, Dist-Jalna

E-mail satish_dhoke2000@yahoo.com

Somani Pravin

Research Scholar, Dept. of Management Science
Dr. B.A.M. University Aurangabad

INTRODUCTION

Entrepreneurship is one of the four mainstream economic factors: Land, labor, capital, and entrepreneurship. The word itself, derived from 17th-century French *entreprenre*, which means to 'undertake' - those who "undertake" the risk of new enterprise. They are "contractor" who bear the risk of profit and loss. Early entrepreneurs were soldiers of fortune, adventurers, builders, merchants, and, incidentally, funeral directors. How the term "undertaker" became associated with funerals is a mystery, but there is a considerable body of literature on entrepreneurship. Early references to the entrepreneur in the 14th century speak about tax contractors-individuals who paid a fixed sum of money to a government for the license to collect taxes in their region. Tax entrepreneurs bore the risk of collecting individual taxes, if they collected more than the sum paid for their licenses, they made profit and kept the excess. If they failed to collect enough to match the cost of their licenses, they didn't care, because they had already had their money from license fees. Entrepreneurship was a common topic for discussion in economics for much of the 18th and 19th centuries. Notable early French, British, and Austrian economists wrote enthusiastically on entrepreneurs as the "change agents" of progressive economies.

Entrepreneurship defies definition. It is very difficult to find an exclusive definition for it. However, Schumpeter provides us with a framework for understanding both in terms of process. Schumpeter's suggests that the role of an entrepreneur is, "to reform or revolutionize the pattern of production by exploiting an invention or, more generally, an untried technological possibility for producing a new commodity or producing an old one in a new way" (Entrepreneurship 7)

Schumpeter does not equate entrepreneurs with inventors, suggesting instead that an inventor might only create a new product, whereas an entrepreneur will gather resources, organize talent, and provide leadership to make the product a commercial success.

Peter Drucker shares Schumpeter's view. He describes the entrepreneurial role as one of gathering and using resources, but he views that "resources, to produce results, must be allocated opportunities rather than to problems" (Entrepreneurship 8)

In Drucker's view entrepreneurship occurs when resources are redirected to progressive opportunities, not used to ensure administrative efficiency. This redirection of resources distinguishes the entrepreneurial role from that of the traditional management role, distinction. That Henry Ford made in his decisions.

Robert Ronstadt's definition of entrepreneurship appears somewhat conclusive: he defines, "Entrepreneurship is the dynamic process of creating incremental wealth. This wealth is created by individuals who assume the major risks in terms of equity, time, and or career commitment of providing value for some product or service. The product or service itself may or may not be new or unique but value must somehow be infused by the entrepreneur by securing and allocating the necessary skills and resources". In contemporary times and entrepreneur is looked upon as an innovator, But to view and entrepreneurship as an innovator raises many questions.